

Applying Baamboozle to teach English vocabulary for pre-starter level at a language center in HCMC

Do Ngoc Lan¹, Nguyen Xuan Hong²

^{1,2}Industrial University of Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam

ABSTRACT: This study investigates the effectiveness of Baamboozle, a digital game-based learning tool, in teaching English vocabulary to Pre-Starter level students at Phuong Nam Language Center, Ho Chi Minh City. Quantitative and qualitative methods are employed. Quantitative data was obtained from questionnaires and tests while qualitative data was collected from interviews. 88 Pre-Starter level students and 17 teachers at Phuong Nam Language Center, Ho Chi Minh City participated in the research. The findings reveal that Baamboozle significantly improves students' vocabulary acquisition and students' engagement compared to traditional methods. Both teachers and students expressed a positive attitude toward the Bamboozle tool, appreciating its interactive and enjoyable nature. However, the study also highlights some challenges when using the tool such as inconsistent use across classes and content repetitiveness. The study recommends regular integration of Baamboozle into English lessons supported by teacher training, and suggests further research on its long-term effects in language learning. This study adds valuable insights into the use of educational technology to enhance language instruction.

KEYWORDS: Attitude, Baamboozle, game-based learning tool, Pre-Starter level, Vocabulary acquisition.

INTRODUCTION

The demand for English language education has rapidly increased in Vietnam, especially for young learners. Vocabulary is the cornerstone of English language acquisition (Adamson, 2004; Asgari & Mustapha, 2011). Having a large store of vocabulary can make communication more fluid and accurate, allowing people to communicate ideas and improve their listening, speaking, reading, and writing abilities (Cervatiuc, 2008). However, many English learners become perplexed when learning vocabulary since there are always new terms. Furthermore, students are unable to find acceptable words to express themselves. Worse, it appears that no amount of time spent reciting the words will help students recall the vocabulary (Drent & Meelissen, 2008). Is there any method for everyone to acquire English vocabulary in a fun way?

Flashcards, taking notes, learning using affixes, and so on are methods for acquiring English vocabulary (J. Harris, 2005; S. Harris, 2002). Some teachers and students employ collocations, association, or extended reading approaches (Jonassen, Carr, & Hsiu-Ping, 1998). Whatever strategy is employed, it is critical to first achieve the study goal, and then learners may select their best vocabulary acquisition tactics.

Baamboozle is an interactive online game that engages learners through various activities such as quizzes, puzzles, and flashcards. It offers an enjoyable and immersive learning experience while promoting active participation and retention of vocabulary. For instance, in a study conducted by Iskandar et al. (2022), students who used Baamboozle in English vocabulary lessons demonstrated increased motivation and better retention of new words compared to those in traditional learning environments. Additionally, teachers have reported that the game-like format fosters a positive learning atmosphere (Arini & Suwarso, 2024).

The paper aims to explore how Baamboozle can be integrated into the curriculum at a Language Center for pre-starter level students. It seeks to investigate its effectiveness in improving vocabulary acquisition among these learners by analyzing their progress throughout the study period. By conducting this research, valuable insights can be gained regarding the potential benefits of incorporating gamified approaches like Baamboozle into language education programs. The findings may contribute to enhancing teaching methodologies for English language instruction at similar educational institutions or even inspire further exploration into other innovative tools or techniques for effective vocabulary instruction at beginner levels.

In this context, the application of Baamboozle, a versatile educational platform, presents an opportunity to revolutionize the teaching of English vocabulary. Baamboozle offers interactive games and activities that can be customized to suit the learning objectives and preferences of students. By integrating Baamboozle into the curriculum at Phuong Nam Language Center, teachers

can create dynamic and engaging learning experiences that facilitate vocabulary retention and comprehension among pre-starter level learners.

However, the effectiveness of implementing Baamboozle for teaching English vocabulary at the pre-starter level needs to be empirically evaluated. Questions arise regarding the impact of Baamboozle on students' vocabulary acquisition, engagement level, and overall learning outcomes. Additionally, factors such as teacher training, technical support, and resource availability may influence the successful integration of Baamboozle into the curriculum.

Based on these considerations, a research study was decided to conduct with the title “*Applying Baamboozle to teach English vocabulary for pre-starter level at a Language Center in Ho Chi Minh City*”. This research is aimed to make a meaningful contribution to the teaching of English in schools and language centres, especially vocabulary teaching.

Research questions

1. Do the teachers at Phuong Nam Language Center use Baamboozle in their teaching practices? If so, how effective?
2. What is the students' attitude towards the use of Baamboozle?
3. What is the teachers' attitude towards the use of Baamboozle?

METHODS

Research design is crucial in determining the effectiveness of a study. Qualitative and quantitative approaches have distinctive purposes and methodologies. In qualitative research, the focus is on understanding the experiences and perspectives of participants. This approach is often used to explore the "why" behind a phenomenon, correlation, or behaviour, by collecting, comparing, and analyzing detailed testimonies from informants (Hoover, 2021). On the other hand, quantitative research involves systematic measurement and analysis of data to produce a statistical overview of trends or relationships. This approach typically addresses the "what" and "how" questions and can confirm or refute hypotheses through numerical data and statistical analysis. Quantitative research results can reveal patterns that suggest causal relationships, which can influence further investigation or action.

Student participants

A total of 88 pre-starter level students were initially considered for the study. From this population, a random sampling method was employed to select 44 students for the experimental group and 44 students for the control group. The experimental group received vocabulary instruction through Baamboozle, a technology-based game, while the control group followed the traditional method of vocabulary learning without the use of Baamboozle.

Experimental Group

This group consisted of 44 students who were exposed to vocabulary learning using Baamboozle. The use of this interactive tool aimed to enhance their engagement and retention of new vocabulary.

Control Group

This group also included 44 students who were taught vocabulary using conventional methods. This approach served as a baseline to compare the effectiveness of the Baamboozle tool in the experimental group.

Questionnaire participants

Out of the total 88 students involved in the study, all 44 students from experimental group participated in the questionnaire. The questionnaire was designed to gather insights into the students' experiences, engagement levels, and overall attitudes toward the methods of vocabulary instruction they were exposed to. This data was essential in assessing the effectiveness of Baamboozle as compared to traditional teaching methods and in understanding student preferences and challenges in learning new vocabulary.

The random selection of students ensured that each student had an equal chance of being assigned to either the experimental or control group, thus minimizing selection bias and enhancing the validity of the study results. The comprehensive data collected from the questionnaire provided a robust basis for analyzing the impact of Baamboozle on vocabulary acquisition and student engagement.

Teacher participants

For the teacher participants, 17 teachers from Phuong Nam Language Center were initially selected to complete a questionnaire designed to gather their attitudes and perceptions regarding the use of Baamboozle in teaching. From these 17 teachers, a

purposive sampling method was used to select 10 teachers for in-depth interviews. This method was chosen to ensure that the selected teachers had diverse experiences and perspectives relevant to the research questions.

Questionnaire participants

All 17 teachers completed a detailed questionnaire that provided quantitative data on their attitudes towards and experiences with Baamboozle. The questionnaire covered aspects such as perceived effectiveness, ease of use, and overall satisfaction with the tool.

Interview participants

Out of the 17 teachers, 10 were purposively selected for interviews. These teachers were chosen based on their varying levels of experience, teaching styles, and familiarity with technology-based teaching tools. The interviews aimed to gather qualitative data that would offer deeper insights into the teachers' attitudes and experiences with Baamboozle.

The combination of random and purposive sampling techniques was employed to achieve a comprehensive understanding of the research questions. A random sampling of students ensured that the study results could be generalized to the broader student population at the pre-starter level. Purposive sampling of teachers allowed for the selection of participants who could provide rich, detailed data pertinent to the study objectives.

By employing these sampling procedures, the study aimed to balance the need for generalizable findings with the depth of understanding required to explore the nuanced perspectives of both students and teachers regarding the use of technology-based games in language learning.

Research instruments

To collect the necessary data for this study, several research instruments were utilized including questionnaires for students and teachers, interviews with teachers, and pre-tests and post-tests conducted over an 8-week period for both the control and experimental groups. The combination of these instruments aimed to provide a comprehensive understanding of the impact of Baamboozle on vocabulary learning and the perceptions of both students and teachers.

Pre-test and Post-test

To evaluate the effectiveness of using Baamboozle in vocabulary learning, pre-tests and post-tests were administered to both the experimental and control groups. These tests designed were based on the reading and writing sections of the Cambridge Starters exam, consisting of five parts with five questions each. The duration for both the pre-test and post-test was 20 minutes.

Experimental Group

Students in the experimental group learned vocabulary using Baamboozle over an 8-week period. The aim was to measure the improvement in their vocabulary retention and usage. The pre-test was given before the introduction of Baamboozle, and the post-test was administered after the 8-week period of using the tool. The results from these tests were then compared to assess the impact of Baamboozle on students' vocabulary learning.

Control Group

Students in the control group followed traditional vocabulary learning methods without the use of Baamboozle. They also took the same pre-test before the 8-week period and the same post-test after 8 weeks. This comparison between the control and experimental groups helped in identifying the differences in vocabulary acquisition and retention due to the use of Baamboozle.

The scores were then analysed to determine the improvement in vocabulary. The pre-tests and post-tests were scored out of 25 points, with each correct answer receiving one point and were evaluated using a shield system, which is commonly used in the Cambridge Starters exam. The scoring criteria were as follows:

Shield	Reading & Writing score	Listening score
2	13	11
3	16	13
4	19	16
5	21	18

Figure 3.1. Shields in Pre-A1 Starters

The design and administration of the pre-tests and post-tests followed established guidelines for educational assessment (Hatch & Lazaraton, 1991) to ensure their validity and reliability. Test items were carefully selected to align with the instructional content and objectives, and pilot testing was conducted to refine the tests and improve their accuracy.

The quantitative data from the pre-tests and post-tests were analysed using statistical techniques to identify any significant differences in vocabulary improvement between the experimental and control groups. This analysis provided a rigorous assessment of the effectiveness of Baamboozle in enhancing students' vocabulary learning outcomes.

RESULTS

The use of Baamboozle by teachers at a Language Center

Teaching experience and grade levels taught:

The teaching experience of the educators at a Language Center varies significantly. Out of the 17 teachers surveyed, 2 have less than 1 year of experience, 5 have between 1 and 3 years, 3 have 3 to 5 years, and the largest group, comprising 7 teachers, has more than 5 years of experience. This diversity in teaching experience indicates a broad range of perspectives on the effectiveness of tools like Baamboozle.

The grade levels taught by these teachers are also diverse. The majority teach at the Pre-Starters level (17 teachers), while the number of teachers decreases progressively at higher levels: Starters (15 teachers), Movers (11 teachers), Flyers (13 teachers), and only 1 teacher handling the Ket + Pet levels. This distribution suggests that Baamboozle is mainly used at the lower to intermediate levels, which could be related to its ease of use and adaptability to younger learners.

Figure 4.1. Distribution of teachers by grade levels taught at Phuong Nam Language Center

English teaching qualifications:

Regarding qualifications, the majority of the teachers possess formal English teaching credentials, with 10 holding a Bachelor's degree, 2 having a College diploma, and 1 teacher holding a Master's degree. Interestingly, 4 teachers do not have any formal English teaching qualifications, which could impact their reliance on user-friendly tools like Baamboozle.

Awareness and use of Baamboozle:

Awareness of Baamboozle among teachers is notably high, with 15 out of 17 teachers knowing about the tool. A similar number are aware of its use as a teaching tool. However, slightly fewer, 13 teachers, have actually used Baamboozle in their teaching. This indicates that while awareness is widespread, actual use may depend on various factors such as perceived effectiveness or the teacher's familiarity with the tool.

Among those who have used Baamboozle, using frequency varies. Only 1 teacher reported always using it, while 4 usually use it, 7 sometimes, and 5 rarely use the tool. This varied frequency might reflect differences in teaching styles, the needs of their students, or the specific challenges and limitations they encounter with the tool.

Figure 4.2. The frequency of Baamboozle use among teachers

Effectiveness of Baamboozle:

The teachers' perception of Baamboozle's effectiveness is overwhelmingly positive, reflecting a strong endorsement of the tool's impact on student learning. Out of the 17 teachers surveyed, 16 believe that Baamboozle is effective in enhancing students' learning experiences. This near-unanimous agreement suggests that Baamboozle has been successfully integrated into the instructional practices at Phuong Nam Language Center, with most educators recognizing its benefits in engaging students and reinforcing learning.

When asked specifically about Baamboozle's effectiveness in enhancing student engagement, the feedback was notably favourable. 10 teachers rated Baamboozle as effective, indicating that it significantly contributes to keeping students actively involved in their lessons. Additionally, 4 teachers went further, rating it as extremely effective, suggesting that for these educators, Baamboozle not only meets but exceeds expectations in creating a dynamic and interactive classroom environment.

Similarly, when evaluating Baamboozle's impact on improving student learning outcomes, the response was highly positive. Twelve teachers found the tool effective in this regard, indicating that Baamboozle plays a crucial role in helping students achieve better academic results. Two teachers even rated it as extremely effective, reinforcing the idea that Baamboozle can be a powerful tool in driving student success when used appropriately.

However, it's important to note that the positive perception of Baamboozle is not universal. One teacher expressed that they did not find Baamboozle effective at all, either in enhancing student engagement or in improving learning outcomes. This dissenting view highlights that while Baamboozle is generally well-regarded, its effectiveness may vary depending on factors such as teaching style, classroom dynamics, or specific student needs.

Primary use and perceived benefits of Baamboozle:

Baamboozle is primarily used for vocabulary practice, with 16 teachers indicating this as its main use. Other uses include grammar exercises (8 teachers), reading comprehension (7 teachers), and speaking practice (5 teachers). Writing exercises and listening activities are less frequently addressed, with 3 teachers each using Baamboozle for these purposes.

The specific aspects of Baamboozle that teachers find most beneficial include its interactive nature (10 teachers), the variety of games available (14 teachers), ease of use (11 teachers), and the immediate feedback it provides (6 teachers). Customizability is also valued by 4 teachers, though it is not the most commonly cited benefit.

Figure 4.3. The primary uses of Baamboozle and the aspects teachers find most beneficial

Challenges and limitations:

Despite its many benefits, 3 teachers reported challenges when using Baamboozle. These challenges include the need to pay for more games and concerns about the accuracy and appropriateness of content, given that Baamboozle allows user-generated content, which may not always be validated by educators. These issues underline the importance of critical evaluation when selecting games and materials for classroom use.

Teachers' attitude towards the use of Baamboozle

General attitudes towards Baamboozle:

The teachers at a Language Center demonstrate a largely positive attitude towards Baamboozle, recognizing its potential to enhance teaching effectiveness and student engagement. Most teachers who are familiar with Baamboozle view it as a valuable educational tool that can make lessons more interactive and enjoyable.

Teacher 1 believes that Baamboozle makes students more interested in learning: "Yes, because it makes students more interested." This sentiment is echoed by Teacher 2, who asserts, "Absolutely." Teacher 3 provides a detailed rationale, highlighting the effectiveness of game-based learning: "When it comes to engaging students, incorporating games into lesson plans can be highly effective. Considering that students generally enjoy games, utilizing them as part of our teaching approach can improve their level of engagement and interest in the material. Therefore, it would be beneficial for teachers to integrate game-based learning activities into our lesson plans as an alternative to traditional reading-based instruction." This perspective underscores the tool's potential to energize the classroom and enhance student interaction.

Perceptions of effectiveness:

Teachers using Baamboozle report that they find it effective for various aspects of teaching. For instance, Teacher 1, who uses Baamboozle “*sometimes, mainly for vocabulary practice,*” noting that “*It’s a great way to engage students and make learning fun.*” Similarly, Teacher 6 mentions that Baamboozle is “*particularly effective during the revision phase of our lessons*” and appreciates its role in fostering a collaborative learning environment through group activities. Teacher 3 observes that Baamboozle’s interactive elements, such as “*visual and interactive elements,*” aid in vocabulary retention and boost participation, especially among quieter students.

Teacher 4 acknowledges Baamboozle’s strengths: “*I think Baamboozle can be effective in teaching/ reviewing vocabulary because it has a wide range of pictures or GIFs that can support the teacher's lesson planning and preparation.*” Teacher 10 shares a similar view, stating that Baamboozle “*makes students more engaged and interested in the lesson by providing fun activities for reviewing and practising,*” thus contributing to a lively and dynamic classroom atmosphere.

Varied use and opinions:

The frequency and manner of Baamboozle’s use vary among teachers. Teacher 2, who uses Baamboozle “*usually for review sessions*” appreciates the competitive aspect of the tool. This approach not only reinforces learning but also engages students more effectively. On the other hand, Teacher 4 has used Baamboozle “*rarely*” primarily for introducing new concepts, indicating that while the tool is beneficial, it is not always a regular part of their teaching routine. Teacher 5, who rarely uses Baamboozle, prefers traditional methods, although they acknowledge that students seem to enjoy the tool.

Teacher 8 reports using Baamboozle “*usually in my lessons, especially for vocabulary and grammar drills*” and finds it effective for both introducing new material and reinforcing it. They note that students who struggle with traditional exercises often perform better with Baamboozle, which encourages its regular use in their teaching practice.

Recommendations for other teachers:

The general consensus among teachers is that Baamboozle is a useful tool that other educators should consider incorporating. Teacher 1 and Teacher 2 both agree that “*Other teachers can apply the Baamboozle as a teaching tool*”. Teacher 3 advocates for Baamboozle as “*an awesome alternative teaching technique*”, particularly for vocabulary mastery. Teacher 4 highlights the game-based nature of Baamboozle as a motivating factor: “*This platform is game-based learning to keep students engaged and motivated.*” However, Teacher 5 is less emphatic, suggesting that while Baamboozle is useful, it is not crucial: “*I think so, but it's still ok if we don't. It isn't that important.*”

Willingness to share experiences:

A majority of teachers who find Baamboozle effective are willing to share their experiences with colleagues. Teacher 1 and Teacher 2 are enthusiastic about sharing, with Teacher 1 stating, “*Yes, I am very willing*” and Teacher 2 affirming, “*Of course*”. Teacher 4 encourages peers to “*take advantage of its flexibility*” and create tailored quizzes, emphasizing the tool’s versatility. Teacher 7, however, expresses a preference for learning from others rather than sharing their own limited experience: “*No, I don't think I have experience enough to share with other teachers. But I want to learn more from other teachers.*”

Students’ attitude towards the use of Baamboozle

Questionnaire results:

The questionnaire was administered to 44 students belonging to the experimental group who got familiar with Baamboozle use in class, ranging in age from 6 to 11 years old, with a fairly balanced gender distribution (23 females and 21 males). The purpose was to assess their experiences and perceptions of using Baamboozle in their English language learning. The following analysis provides insights into the students' responses.

Age and duration of English study:

The participants were spread across different age groups: 6-year-old (4 students), 7-year-old (13 students), 8-year-old (11 students), 9-year-old (5 students), 10-year-old (5 students), and 11-year-old (6 students). The majority of students had been studying English for 1-2 years (24 students), while a significant number had been studying for less than a year (19 students). Only one student reported having studied English for more than two years. This distribution reflects a relatively young and diverse group in terms of experience with the English language.

Figure 4.4. Age distribution of students

Awareness and use of Baamboozle:

An overwhelming majority of students (42 out of 44) were familiar with Baamboozle, and 41 reported that their teacher used it in class. The frequency of use varied, with most students indicating that Baamboozle was used "sometimes" (20 students) or "rarely" (13 students). Only 3 students reported that it was "always" used, while 8 students said it was "usually" used. This suggests that while Baamboozle is a common tool in the classroom, its use is not consistent across all lessons.

Figure 4.5. Frequency of Baamboozle use in class

Activities and preferences:

Students reported that Baamboozle was primarily used for learning new words (35 students) and practising grammar (23 students). It was less frequently used for listening activities (10 students), speaking practice (15 students), reading exercises (10 students), and writing exercises (9 students). A few students (3) mentioned its use for reviewing old lessons or exam preparation. This indicates that Baamboozle is most effective in vocabulary and grammar instruction, but its application in other language skills is somewhat limited.

Enjoyment and effectiveness:

When asked about their enjoyment of using Baamboozle, a majority of students (34 out of 44) expressed positive feelings, with 20 students indicating they "like" it and 14 students stating they "very like" it. Only one student reported disliking it, and 10 students were neutral. The most commonly cited reasons for liking Baamboozle included making learning fun (28 students), helping to remember vocabulary better (17 students), encouraging participation (15 students), fostering interaction with classmates (18 students), and boosting confidence in English skills (20 students). However, some students found Baamboozle to be repetitive (11 students), not engaging enough (7 students), or difficult to use (3 students).

Figure 4.6. Student enjoyment of Baamboozle in English learning

Perceived impact on learning:

A significant majority of students (42 out of 44) believed that Baamboozle helped improve their English learning results, particularly in vocabulary (38 students), grammar (20 students), speaking (15 students), listening (11 students), reading (10 students), and writing (9 students). In terms of overall effectiveness, 39 students rated Baamboozle as either "effective" or "extremely effective," with none rating it as "not effective at all" Additionally, all students reported being ready to learn English when Baamboozle was used, indicating a high level of engagement and motivation associated with this tool.

Pre-test and Post-test results

The pre-test and post-test results were conducted on two groups: the experimental group and the control group. The objective of comparing these results is to evaluate the impact of the new teaching method applied to the experimental group.

Table 4.1. Descriptive statistics of the control group and experimental students and the experimental group students' mean scores before and after the treatment

Pre-test and Post-test	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	94% Confidence interval of the difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Control group	-1.045	1.133	0.171	-1.380	-0.710	-6.11	43	.000
Experimental group	-4.045	1.133	0.171	-4.380	-3.710	-23.71	43	.000

The mean calculation of the differences between the Pre-test and Post-test scores shows a significant change between the two groups. Specifically, the mean value for the experimental group is -4.045, while the control group has a mean value of only -

1.045. This reflects that the experimental group experienced a greater change in scores after participating in the experiment, indicating that the new method had a significant impact. In contrast, the smaller change in the control group suggests that the traditional teaching method had little impact on students' learning outcomes.

The standard deviation (Std. Deviation) for both groups is the same at 1.133. This standard deviation reflects the degree of dispersion of scores around the mean. The similar standard deviation in both groups indicates that the variability in scores among students within each group is relatively consistent. This means that both groups exhibited consistent levels of score changes, although the experimental group tended to show a larger change.

The standard error of the mean (Std. Error Mean) in both groups is 0.171. This small standard error indicates that the mean values are estimated with high accuracy. A low standard error suggests that there is little variability in how the mean values were calculated, allowing us to confidently assert that the differences in scores within each group are reliably determined.

The 94% confidence interval of the difference for both groups provides additional information on the reliability of these results. For the experimental group, the confidence interval ranges from -4.380 to -3.710, indicating that the true mean difference is likely to fall within this range. For the control group, the confidence interval ranges from -1.380 to -0.710, showing that the true mean difference in this group is significantly smaller than that of the experimental group. The narrow confidence intervals for both groups further reinforce confidence in the accuracy of the research results.

The t-test value is another important aspect of this analysis. The t value for the experimental group is -23.71, while the control group has a t value of -6.11. The larger the absolute t-test value, the more pronounced the difference between Pre-test and Post-test scores. The large t value for the experimental group indicates that the new teaching method has led to a significant change in the scores of this group, compared to the less pronounced change in the control group.

The Sig. (2-tailed) value for both groups is .000, indicating that the difference between Pre-test and Post-test scores is statistically significant at the 5% significance level. This means that we can reject the null hypothesis that there is no difference between Pre-test and Post-test scores in both groups. In other words, the new teaching method has had a clear and measurable impact, and this difference is not due to chance.

To further explore the data, additional metrics such as min (minimum value), max (maximum value), mean (average value), and standard deviation were calculated for both groups:

Table 4.2. Summary of Pre-test and Post-test score statistics for control and experimental groups

Group	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Deviation
Control Group	3	7	5.05	1.133
Experimental Group	1	9	5.36	1.133

Control group analysis:

- + The min score was 3, indicating that some students had lower scores even after participating in both Pre-test and Post-test.
- + The max score was 7, showing that the highest score in the control group did not reach the maximum possible score.
- + The mean score was 5.05, reflecting that the students' performance in this group had a limited improvement after the tests.
- + The standard deviation was 1.133, indicating a relatively tight distribution of scores around the mean, suggesting consistency among students' scores.

Experimental group analysis:

- + The min score was 1, indicating that at least one student had very low scores, either in the Pre-test or Post-test, possibly reflecting an outlier or a unique case where the new method was ineffective.
- + The max score was 9, showing that some students achieved very high scores, demonstrating a significant improvement after applying the new teaching method.
- + The mean score was 5.36, slightly higher than the control group, suggesting that the new teaching method had a positive impact, though not overwhelmingly so.

- + The standard deviation was also 1.133, similar to the control group, indicating that the spread of scores around the mean was consistent, with some students showing exceptional performance and others less so.

This analysis suggests that although the experimental group showed more improvement than the control group, the differences were not vast. The mean score for the experimental group was higher, but both groups had similar levels of variability (standard deviation) in their scores. This indicates that the new teaching method may have benefited some students significantly, while others might not have experienced as much of an improvement.

DISCUSSIONS

The synthesis of findings from the questionnaires, interviews, and tests' results offers a comprehensive view of Baamboozle's impact and effectiveness in English language teaching at Phuong Nam Language Center. This section integrates the data to address the overall research questions and draw meaningful conclusions.

Synthesis of results

Teacher usage of Baamboozle:

The data collected from the questionnaires reveals that a significant majority of students (41 out of 44) report that their teachers use Baamboozle during English lessons. Interviews with teachers further elucidate that Baamboozle is primarily utilized for vocabulary instruction and grammar practice. The varying frequencies of Baamboozle's use, with many students indicating "sometimes" or "rarely," suggest that while Baamboozle is recognized as a valuable tool, its application is inconsistent across different classes. This observation aligns with the questionnaire data, indicating that although Baamboozle is widely acknowledged and used, its integration into the curriculum varies significantly.

Student attitudes toward Baamboozle:

The questionnaire data reveals that most students have a positive attitude towards Baamboozle, with 34 out of 44 expressing enjoyment in using the platform. Students appreciate Baamboozle for making learning enjoyable, aiding in vocabulary retention, and boosting their confidence. Interviews with students confirm these findings, highlighting that Baamboozle's interactive and gamified approach is well-received. However, some students reported challenges such as repetitiveness and occasional difficulties with the platform, which were also noted in the questionnaire responses. These issues suggest that while Baamboozle is generally well-regarded, there is room for improvement to enhance engagement and effectiveness.

Effectiveness in learning:

According to the questionnaire results, 42 students believe that Baamboozle positively impacts their English learning outcomes, particularly in vocabulary and grammar. This perception is supported by the pre-test and post-test results, which indicate noticeable improvements in students' vocabulary and grammar skills following the use of Baamboozle. The effectiveness ratings, with most students finding Baamboozle "effective" or "extremely effective," align with the observed enhancements in test scores. This synthesis of data confirms that Baamboozle is perceived as a valuable educational tool that significantly contributes to language learning.

Impact on learning engagement and motivation:

The combined findings from the questionnaires and interviews suggest that Baamboozle has a positive effect on student engagement and motivation. Students reported feeling more confident and engaged during lessons where Baamboozle was used, and their readiness to learn increased when this tool was incorporated. The pre-test and post-test results demonstrate a correlation between increased engagement and improved learning outcomes, reinforcing the role of Baamboozle in making English learning more engaging and motivating for students.

Use of Baamboozle by teachers:

The data confirms that Baamboozle is widely used by teachers at Phuong Nam Language Center, primarily for vocabulary and grammar instruction. However, the frequency and consistency of its use vary, indicating that while Baamboozle is a prevalent tool, its integration could be optimized across different classes to ensure uniform application.

Students' attitudes toward Baamboozle:

Students generally have a favourable attitude toward Baamboozle, appreciating its interactive and enjoyable nature. Despite some criticisms related to the repetitiveness of the content and difficulties with the platform, the overall sentiment is positive. This suggests that Baamboozle is effective in engaging students and enhancing their learning experience.

Teachers' attitudes toward Baamboozle:

The data from interviews and questionnaires indicates that teachers value Baamboozle for its role in vocabulary and grammar instruction. They recognize its benefits but also acknowledge the need for more consistent integration to maximize its potential. Teachers' feedback highlights the importance of addressing challenges and improving the tool's application in the classroom.

Effectiveness of Baamboozle:

The integration of results from questionnaires, interviews, and test scores demonstrates that Baamboozle is effective in improving students' English learning outcomes. The positive feedback from students and the improvements observed in test results validate the tool's effectiveness in enhancing vocabulary, grammar, and overall language skills.

In comparing the findings from this study on the use of Baamboozle in English language teaching at Phuong Nam Language Center with existing literature, several notable similarities, differences, and new insights emerge. This analysis provides a broader understanding of how Baamboozle fits into the current landscape of educational technology and gamification.

Positive impact on engagement and motivation:

The study's findings confirm that Baamboozle enhances student engagement and motivation, aligning with established research. Berna Karakoç (2022) conducted a meta-analysis that highlights the effectiveness of game-based learning in increasing student achievement and motivation. Similarly, Warschauer and Healey (1998) have emphasized the role of interactive and digital tools in fostering greater student involvement. This study supports these conclusions, as students reported heightened engagement and motivation when using Baamboozle. The interactive nature of the tool seems to contribute significantly to maintaining student interest and enthusiasm, reinforcing the positive impact of gamified learning environments.

Effectiveness in vocabulary and grammar:

The study also aligns with the literature regarding the effectiveness of digital tools in enhancing vocabulary and grammar. Schmitt (2000) and Nation (2008) have shown that educational tools play a crucial role in vocabulary acquisition and language learning. This study supports these findings by demonstrating that students showed measurable improvements in vocabulary and grammar after engaging with Baamboozle. The positive outcomes reported here are consistent with the broader research on the benefits of integrating digital platforms into language instruction.

Frequency of use:

One area where this study diverges from existing literature is in the frequency of Baamboozle's use. While research by Dörnyei and Taguchi (2009) emphasizes the importance of consistent and frequent use of educational tools for maximizing their benefits, this study reveals that the use of Baamboozle was inconsistent across different classes. This variability suggests that while the tool has potential, its impact may be diminished if not used regularly. The discrepancy between recommended practices and actual implementation highlights a gap that could be addressed through a more systematic integration of Baamboozle into the curriculum.

Student challenges with repetitiveness:

Another notable difference is the issue of repetitiveness identified in this study. Although earlier research, such as J. Harris (2005), often reports high satisfaction with gamified learning tools, this study found that students perceived Baamboozle as repetitive at times. This contrasts with the generally positive feedback reported in other studies and suggests that while Baamboozle is effective, it may benefit from modifications to reduce monotony and enhance user experience. Addressing this concern could improve the tool's overall effectiveness and user satisfaction.

Variable integration in curriculum:

This study offers new insights into the variable integration of Baamboozle across different classes. The finding that Baamboozle's use is inconsistent contrasts with the literature, which often assumes a more uniform application of educational tools. Research by Cameron (2001) and others typically presume that educational tools are implemented consistently across settings. This study highlights the need for a more structured and consistent integration of Baamboozle to ensure that all students benefit equally from its features. The variability observed in this study suggests that a more systematic approach could enhance the overall impact of the tool.

Detailed student feedback on usability:

The study provides detailed feedback on usability challenges, such as difficulties with the tool and lack of engagement. This adds a new dimension to the discussion of educational tools. While existing literature often focuses on general effectiveness and

engagement, this study sheds light on specific areas where Baamboozle could be improved. Insights into usability issues provide valuable information for refining the tool and addressing user concerns, which could lead to better outcomes and a more positive experience for students.

CONCLUSIONS

Diverse Teaching Experience and Grade Levels:

Teachers at a Language Center vary widely in teaching experience and the levels they teach. Baamboozle is predominantly used by teachers at the Pre-Starters level, which aligns with its design as an interactive and user-friendly tool suitable for young learners.

High awareness, varied use:

Awareness of Baamboozle among teachers is high, with the majority having used it at least occasionally. However, the frequency of use varies, with only a small number of teachers using it regularly.

Perceived effectiveness:

Teachers generally perceive Baamboozle as an effective tool for enhancing student engagement and improving learning outcomes. Most teachers report that Baamboozle is particularly effective in making lessons more interactive and enjoyable.

Positive attitude towards integration:

The majority of teachers hold a positive attitude towards integrating Baamboozle into their teaching practices. They believe it helps make lessons more engaging and supports vocabulary learning effectively.

Varied implementation:

While most teachers find Baamboozle beneficial, the extent of its use and the specific ways it is integrated into lessons vary among teachers. Some use it primarily for review sessions, while others incorporate it regularly into different aspects of their teaching.

Willingness to share:

Teachers who find Baamboozle effective are generally willing to share their experiences with colleagues, indicating a collaborative approach to adopting new teaching tools.

Significant improvement in vocabulary acquisition:

The comparison of pre-test and post-test results between the experimental group (using Baamboozle) and the control group (using traditional methods) shows a significant improvement in vocabulary acquisition for the experimental group. This suggests that Baamboozle is an effective tool for enhancing vocabulary learning among young students.

Positive reception among students:

The majority of students are familiar with and enjoy using Baamboozle. They find it to be a fun and engaging way to learn English, which supports the tool's effectiveness in creating a positive learning environment.

An effective tool for young learners:

The study concludes that Baamboozle is an effective tool for teaching English vocabulary to young learners, particularly at the Pre-Starters level. Its interactive nature and ease of use make it a valuable addition to traditional teaching methods.

Need for tailored implementation:

While the overall feedback is positive, the varied usage among teachers suggests that successful integration of Baamboozle into classroom practice may require tailored approaches that consider the specific needs and preferences of both teachers and students. This study explored the use of Baamboozle as a digital tool for teaching English vocabulary, focusing on its effectiveness and the attitudes of both teachers and students. The findings indicate that Baamboozle is a valuable addition to the educational toolkit, offering significant benefits in terms of student engagement, motivation, and vocabulary acquisition.

The positive attitudes of both teachers and students toward Baamboozle suggest that game-based learning tools have a strong potential for enhancing the learning experience. However, the study also highlights the need for further research, particularly in terms of long-term outcomes, comparative effectiveness, and the challenges faced by teachers in integrating such tools into their teaching practices.

In conclusion, Baamboozle represents a promising approach to modernizing language instruction, making it more interactive, enjoyable, and effective. By embracing digital tools and continuing to explore their potential, educators can create more dynamic and inclusive learning environments that cater to the diverse needs of students in the digital age.

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